

Diffusion of Water in Soil under a Temperature Gradient

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A phenomenological description of the process of thermal diffusion has been given. Diffusion equations have been developed from the thermodynamics of irreversible processes, and expressions for fundamental quantities like the entropy-production and the dissipation function for a non-isothermal system have been derived from the first principles. These various rate equations have been shown to yield for isothermal conditions different forms of Darcy's law for flow of soil-water under varying degrees of saturation. The concept of heat of transport is also introduced, and its relevance in relation to soil-water interactions discussed. These various derivations have been followed by a short review of work done thus far to investigate thermal diffusion of water (both in the liquid and the vapour phases) in soil by different workers.

1.1. General Introduction :

THE process of diffusion in a mixture implies a relative motion of the components, that is, a difference in the mean velocities of each species of molecule. Diffusion is most frequently associated with a non-uniformity of composition, but it can also arise from non-uniformity of other properties, in particular, of temperature and pressure. Diffusion induced by a temperature gradient is thermal diffusion.

It has long been known that the simple form of Darcy's law, describing the flow of water in soil under a hydraulic gradient, or a soil-water potential gradient, fails to take into account the influence of forces other than those arising from a differential moisture content, or potential gradient. In particular, the effect of the thermal gradients has been shown to induce the movement of moisture in soil^{1,2,8}, both in the liquid and the vapour phases. As early as 1927, Lebedeff³ observed in a field experiment during Russian winter that more than 6 cm of soil water moved upward into the soil profile in response to the seasonal thermal gradients.

Whether or not this flow of soil-moisture associated with day-night and seasonal temperature cycles is of practical significance, depends upon local conditions. However, there is little doubt that such flow often has considerable practical importance, especially in supplying small amounts of water needed for germination of seeds in dry-land areas.

Surprisingly enough, very little has thus far been done to explore this important phenomenon, in spite of the fact that the diurnal and seasonal temperature fluctuations lead to considerable thermal gradients in soil. The need at this stage of a general theory, encompassing all these various aspects of

soil-water movement, seems obvious. Buckingham, even as early as 1907², recognised this while stating that "a rigorous treatment of the subject, with no restrictions imposed on either the water content or the soluble salt content of the soil, would have to use thermodynamic reasoning. But the simple conception of a mechanical potential will suffice for the present purpose, though it is not impossible that with more comprehensive experimental data available, we should have to use thermodynamic potential, or the free energy". The thermodynamics of irreversible processes appears to be capable of providing such a general theory and understanding of transport process in soil. Indeed, it has proved to be a powerful tool in systems of physics and chemistry for getting at certain general and useful working relations between various fluxes, and the corresponding forces, responsible for them. In the case of soil systems also, Taylor and Cary^{1,2,4} developed a generalised theory of simultaneous transport of heat and matter, and this will be referred to in the following sections.

Several monographs^{5,6,7,15} have already appeared on the subject of irreversible thermodynamics. In the present review, the basic postulates of irreversible thermodynamics will first be recapitulated, with special reference to thermal diffusion. Treatments given follow those of Agar⁷ and Sanyal⁸. This will then be followed by the relevant published work in soil.

1.2. Thermodynamics of Thermal Diffusion :

The relationships for transport phenomena cannot be deduced from classical thermodynamics as it deals with equilibria and reversible processes (hence the name "thermostatistics"⁸). The transport processes are irreversible in nature. One of the starting points of extension of thermodynamics to irreversible

processes is the fact that, according to the empirical laws of Fourier, Ohm and Fick, regarding conduction of heat, electricity and matter, respectively, the correlation between the fluxes and the forces causing them, is linear. In general, the relation between such fluxes (J) and the corresponding thermodynamic forces (X) can be described by a power series of the forces. However, for a state, close to equilibrium (which results for small values of the forces X), it is adequate to retain only the linear term, as confirmed by experiments, i.e.,

$$J=L X \quad \dots (1.2.1)$$

In eq. (1.2.1), L is a phenomenological constant, characteristic of the substance through which flux J occurs, and may be termed its generalised (specific) conductance, or "admittance" (=1/resistance). The forces X are given by the gradients of thermodynamic variables, such as chemical potential[†], electrostatic potential, etc., causing macroscopic flows of heat, matter, or electric charge. These forces are thermodynamic in nature which have got nothing to do with the Newtonian forces in that they do not, in general, impart any acceleration (they might impart acceleration in a special case when they can incorporate a Newtonian force, e.g. sedimentation under gravity).

Furthermore, there may be interaction (coupling) between two or more transport processes, occurring simultaneously in the same system so that a flux density of one kind may result from a force of different kind. Well known examples of such coupled transport processes are thermal diffusion and thermo-osmosis (interaction of mass diffusion and heat conduction), thermo-electricity (Peltier, Seebeck and Thomson effects) electrokinetic phenomena (electro-osmosis, streaming potential, streaming current), isothermal diffusion in electrolyte solutions, etc.

A brief description of the phenomenon of thermal diffusion will now follow. When a temperature gradient exists in a solution, or mixture, of initial uniform composition, a partial de-mixing of the components usually takes place owing to their relative movement. This phenomenon goes under the name of "thermal diffusion", or the "Soret effect" (after Charles Soret, the discoverer of the phenomenon), the latter term being restricted to condensed phases. This systematic relative movement of the components of a solution leads, in

absence of convective re-mixing, to the establishment of concentration gradients, which, in turn, trigger off ordinary (isothermal) diffusion in the opposite direction. Eventually, a steady state is reached when the rates of these opposing processes balance each other, and a time-invariant concentration gradient is established in the system. This steady (or, stationary) state is sometimes referred to as "Soret equilibrium", although it is not a true thermodynamic equilibrium state in that heat continues to pass through the system by thermal conduction. Whereas viscosity, ordinary diffusion, and thermal conductivity are first-order effects, depending primarily on the occurrence of molecular collisions, and only secondarily on the nature of these collisions, thermal diffusion is a second-order effect, which may be positive, negative, or zero, according to the nature of the molecular interactions.

In the present case of thermal diffusion, the flux-densities (J_i) of various components in the system may be defined along with an additional flux-density to characterise the flux of "heat". An entropy flux density (J_s) is defined for this purpose, and all the flux densities are referred to the "solvent", or, what is more commonly known as "Hittorf frame" of reference, so that J_o (solvent) = 0, identically (i.e., the flux-densities represent the rate of transfer of matter and heat across unit area of a surface which "moves with the solvent"). This simplifies the algebra considerably; a more symmetrical treatment, in which *all* J_s might be non-zero and *all* would, therefore, have to be considered, leads to difficulties (for reasons to become apparent shortly) because they would not be linearly independent and the corresponding conjugate forces X would not be linearly independent either. However, in an unsymmetrical reference frame, any other component may be considered stationary, and other flux-densities referred to it, e.g., in soil-water system, $J_{Soil} = 0$ may serve as the reference frame.

At this stage, an energy flux-density (J_u), associated with the flow of matter and heat across the boundary of the system, in question, may also be defined by

$$T J_s = J_u - \sum_i \mu_i J_i \quad \dots (1.2.2)$$

where μ_i is the chemical potential of the component 'i'. It appears from eq. (1.2.2) that J_u possibly may better be regarded as an enthalpy flux-density.

[†] However, it is not obvious how the chemical potential, corresponding to equilibrium states (a quantity of free-energy character), can be applied to the description of the rate of irreversible processes—and among them of diffusion. It is well known, for example, that the rate of chemical reactions is not proportional, in general, to the change of free energy in the process but depends on the kinetic barrier, for instance. However, in a detailed analysis of the problem, Onsager⁹ and de Groot⁵ found that in diffusion the change in free energy resulting from mixing of solutions of various concentrations (which is measured by the chemical potential gradient) can be identified with the work of the diffusing species against the friction of the viscous medium. Since diffusion is a slow process, deviations from the equilibrium state are much smaller in the course of the process than in most of the chemical reactions. Under such conditions, the total change in free energy is almost equal to the energy dissipated by the viscous forces in friction.)

2.1. *The Entropy Flux and the Dissipation Function :*

A relation familiar from thermostatics is the Clausius inequality, namely

$$dS \geq \sum \delta q/T \quad \dots (2.1.1)$$

where S is the entropy, q is the heat transported across a boundary of the system, and T is the temperature of the surrounding at the boundary. The "equality" sign applies to the case of a reversible process, whereas the "greater than" sign applies if the process is irreversible.

It is convenient to transform this relation into an equality by writing

$$dS = d_i S + d_e S \quad \dots (2.1.2)$$

Here, $d_i S$ is the entropy created internally by virtue of the fact that the process is irreversible ($d_i S$ is zero for a reversible process), and $d_e S$ corresponds to the term $\sum \frac{\delta q}{T}$ of eq. (2.1.1), and is the entropy change due to heat flows across the boundaries of the system under consideration.

Dividing by the time-interval dt, it follows from eq. (2.1.2)

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{d_i S}{dt} + \frac{d_e S}{dt} \quad \dots (2.1.3)$$

In terms of the entropy flux-density, J_s , introduced by e.q. (1.2.2), it is possible to write

$$\frac{d_e S}{dt} = - \int_A J_s \cdot dA \quad \dots (2.1.4)$$

where the integral is taken over the area of the system under consideration. Applying Gauss's theorem to eq. (2.1.4) we get

$$\frac{d_e S}{dt} = - \int_V \text{div } J_s \, dV \quad \dots (2.1.5)$$

the integral here being taken over the volume V of the system.

The "local" entropy production per unit volume (θ) due to irreversible processes may now be defined by

$$\int_V \theta \, dV = \frac{d_i S}{dt} \quad \dots (2.1.6)$$

and, thus, on substitution of eqs. (2.1.5) and (2.1.6) into eq. (2.1.3) the result is,

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \int (-\text{div } J_s + \theta) \, dv \quad \dots (2.1.7)$$

This equation may be put into a more useful form by introducing the concept of local entropy density,

defined as the entropy per unit volume, $S_v (S_v = S/V)$. Then, on removing the integral, eq. (2.1.6) becomes

$$\frac{dS_v}{dt} = -\text{div } J_s + \theta \quad \dots (2.1.8)$$

The quantity θ is of fundamental importance in the development of the thermodynamic theory of irreversible processes, and in particular, the fluxes and forces must be so chosen as to satisfy the relation,

$$\phi = T\theta = \sum_i J_i X_i + J_s X_s \quad \dots (2.1.9)$$

where $X_s = -\text{grad } T$

$\phi = T\theta$ is known as a dissipation function which is zero for the equilibrium state, and minimum at the steady state of a non-equilibrium process. In the following section, relation (2.1.9) will be derived for the special case of thermal diffusion.

2.2. *Thermodynamic Description of Non-equilibrium Systems :*

Non-equilibrium systems, in contrast to equilibrium ones, are characterised by gradients of various intensive thermodynamic variables, in particular of temperature and chemical potential (as in thermal diffusion). It is, therefore, apparent that Gibbs equation, eq. (2.2.1)

$$dU = TdS - PdV + \sum_i \mu_i dN_i \quad \dots (2.2.1)$$

where U is the internal energy and N_i the number of moles of the component "i" in the system, cannot be directly applied to such a non-isothermal system, in its entirety. It is in this context necessary to introduce the concept of subsystems.

The total system, in question, is divided into a number of subsystems which are made sufficiently small for local values of thermodynamic variables to be assigned. The degree of "disequilibrium" within each subsystem for this purpose must be small. However, the subsystems are of macroscopic sizes. For these conditions to be fulfilled, certain constraints must be applied while defining a system, to be treated in this manner. Especially, for thermal diffusion, the gradient of temperature must not be too large. Also, the flows of matter must be slow, and not turbulent. Any chemical reaction taking place must be locally in equilibrium at all points in the system.

With the above conditions holding, eq. (2.2.1) can be applied to each of the subsystems defined above. Assigning lower-case symbols to the extensive variables of the system one obtains,

$$du = Tds - Pdv + \sum_i \mu_i dn_i \quad \dots (2.2.2)$$

On integrating eq. (2.2.2) with T, P, and μ_i constant, and $u=0$ for $s=v=n_i=0$, we get

$$u = Ts - Pv + \sum_i \mu_i n_i \quad \dots (2.2.3)$$

Dividing by v and introducing symbols for local concentrations in the same way as already done for entropy, it follows from eq. (2.2.3),

$$u_v = Ts_v - P + \sum_i \mu_i C_i \quad \dots (2.2.4)$$

where C_i is the concentration (mol. cm^{-3}) of 'i' and $C_i = n_i/v$.

Alternatively, it is possible to obtain directly from eq. (2.2.2),

$$d(vu_v) = Td(vs_v) - Pd v + \sum_i \mu_i d(vC_i) \quad \dots (2.2.5)$$

which, on differentiation and rearrangement leads to

$$-v(Tds_v - du_v + \sum_i \mu_i dC_i) = (Ts_v - u_v - P + \sum_i \mu_i dC_i)dv \quad \dots (2.2.6)$$

The right-hand side of eq. (2.2.6) is, by eq. (2.2.4), equal to zero, and hence. $Tds_v = du_v - \sum_i \mu_i dC_i$ (2.2.7). By dividing eq. (2.2.7) throughout by the time-interval dt , this may be put into a form where it is possible to substitute the expressions for the fluxes :

$$T \frac{ds_v}{dt} = \frac{du_v}{dt} - \sum_i \mu_i \frac{dC_i}{dt} \quad \dots (2.2.8)$$

An expression for ds_v/dt (eq. 2.1.8) has already been derived, and so we must obtain expressions for the other two time-derivatives. First consider dC_i/dt .

For the sake of simplicity, it is assumed that no chemical reaction is taking place in the system, producing the species 'i' and these 'i's refer to the components of the system, defined in the phase-rule sense. Thus, the simple relation results,

$$\frac{dn_i}{dt} = - \int J_i \cdot dA \quad \dots (2.2.9)$$

where eq. (2.2.9) refers to one of the subsystems, and the integration is taken over the surface of this subsystem.

As before applying Gauss's theorem, and introducing C_i in place of n_i we find that it is possible to remove the integration, and obtain

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} = - \text{div } J_i \quad \dots (2.2.10)$$

(no chemical reaction)

Now consider du_v/dt . It is obvious that the divergence of the energy flux density, J_u , defined in section 1.2, will contribute to du_v/dt . However, any external forces, e.g. electrostatic forces, etc., which will contribute to this term, must also be taken into consideration. If F_i denotes the force, acting on one mole of component 'i', then the con-

tribution of these external forces to $\frac{du_v}{dt}$ will be F_i .

J_i . Thus on combining these two terms

$$\frac{du_v}{dt} = -\text{div } J_u + \sum_i F_i \cdot J_i \quad \dots (2.2.11)$$

Substituting eqs. (2.1.8), (2.2.10), (2.2.11) into eq. (2.2.8), one obtains

$$T(-\text{div } J_s + \theta) = -\text{div } J_u + \sum_i F_i \cdot J_i + \sum_i \mu_i \text{div } J_i \quad \dots (2.2.12)$$

Applying a well-known relation of vector calculus which states

$$\text{div}(AB) = A \text{div } B + B \cdot \text{grad } A$$

eq. (2.2.12) becomes, on rearrangement,

$$\phi = T\theta = \text{div}(T J_s - J_u + \sum_i \mu_i J_i) - J_s \cdot \text{grad } T - \sum_i J_i \cdot (\text{grad } \mu_i - F_i) \quad (2.2.13)$$

The first term on right-hand side of eq. (2.2.13) is zero by eq. (1.2.2) Hence

$$\phi = T\theta = -J_s \cdot \text{grad } T + \sum_i J_i \cdot \{-(\text{grad } \mu_i - F_i)\} \quad \dots (2.2.14)$$

In case F_i is restricted to electrical forces,

$$F_i = -Z_i F \cdot \text{grad } \psi$$

where F is the Faraday's constant, Z_i is the valence (including sign) of 'i', and ψ is the electrostatic potential at the point, in question, and so

$$\phi = T\theta = J_s \cdot (-\text{grad } T) + \sum_i J_i \cdot \{-(\text{grad } \mu_i + Z_i F \cdot \text{grad } \psi)\} \quad \dots (2.2.15)$$

On comparing eq. (2.2.15) with eq. (2.1.9), the various fluxes and forces may at once be identified:

J_i = Flux of matter.

J_s = Flux of entropy.

X_i = $-(\text{grad } \mu_i + Z_i F \cdot \text{grad } \psi)$... (2.2.16)

X_s = $-\text{grad } T$ ("entropy force") ... (2.2.17)

In case the external forces (F_i) are only gravitational

$$F_i = -M_i \cdot \text{grad } \psi_g$$

where M_i is the molar mass of 'i' and ψ_g is the gravitational potential. In that case

$$X_i = -(\text{grad } \mu_i + M_i \cdot \text{grad } \psi_g)$$

However, there may be another choice of fluxes and forces which is often used by various workers. The expression for X_i (eq. 2.2.16) contains the quantity $\text{grad } \mu_i$ and in this form, it includes the way in which μ_i changes with temperature. In particular

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mu_i}{\partial T}\right) = -S_i \quad \dots (2.2.18)$$

where S_i is the partial molal entropy of 'i'. Thus, it is possible to write

$$\text{grad } \mu_i = (\text{grad } \mu_i)_T + (\partial \mu_i / \partial T) \cdot \text{grad } T$$

(isobaric conditions assumed)

$$= (\text{grad } \mu_i)_T - S_i \cdot \text{grad } T$$

On substituting this into eq. (2.2.14), and rearranging, eq. (2.2.19) is obtained

$$\phi = T\theta = (J_s - \sum_i J_i S_i) (-\text{grad } T) + \sum_i J_i [-\{(\text{grad } \mu_i)_T + Z_i F \cdot \text{grad } \psi\}] \dots (2.2.19)$$

A new flux, the calorimetric heat flux, J_a , may now be defined by

$$\frac{J_a}{T} = J_s - \sum_i J_i S_i \dots (2.2.20)$$

and, so also new forces, by

$$X_a = -\text{grad } T/T \dots (2.2.20)$$

$$X_i = -\{(\text{grad } \mu_i)_T - F_i\} \dots (2.2.22)$$

2.3. Linear Phenomenological Equations :

Let a non-isothermal system of n solutes in a solvent (denoted by subscript 'o') be now considered as introduced in section 1.2. Then, assuming linearity between J 's and X 's, the linear phenomenological equations with the forces X_i and X_s , defined by eqs. (2.2.16) and (2.2.17), are given as

$$J_i = \sum_{j=1}^n L_{ij} X_j + L_{is} X_s \quad (i, j=1 \text{ to } n) \quad (2.3.1)$$

$$J_s = \sum_{j=1}^n L_{sj} X_j + L_{ss} X_s$$

The fluxes are considered in a reference frame defined by $J_o=0$. The diagonal coefficients L_{ii} and L_{ss} give the flux-density of an entity due to its conjugate force, X_i, X_s (L_{ss} is related to the thermal conductivity of the system), while the off-diagonal coefficients represent the coupling, or "cross-effect" coefficients. It is noteworthy that X_o does not appear in eqs. (2.3.1), since X_o can be eliminated for a system in mechanical equilibrium (gradient of pressure being thus equal to total external force per unit volume) with the aid of the Gibbs-Duhem relations between the forces,

$$\sum_{i=0}^n C_i X_i + X_s \sum_{i=0}^n C_i S_i = 0$$

An important postulate of irreversible thermodynamics, known as *Onsager's Reciprocity Relations* (O.R.R.) between "cross-effect" coefficients, $L_{jk} (j \neq k)$, will now be introduced; it states that provided a proper choice is made for the fluxes and the forces, then the matrix of the phenomenological coefficients L_{jk} is symmetric, i.e.,

$$L_{jk} = L_{kj} \quad (j \neq k) \dots (2.3.2)$$

The proper choice is defined by two conditions; the first is that the fluxes and the forces satisfy eq.

(2.1.9) (which is fulfilled by J 's and X 's of eqs. 2.3.1: vide eq. 2.2.15); and secondly, that the fluxes and the forces should be linearly independent (which has been ensured in framing eqs. (2.3.1) by making $J_o=0$, and ignoring X_o).

Since both these conditions are satisfied by the fluxes and the forces of eqs. (2.3.1),

$$L_{ij} = L_{ji} \quad (i \neq j), \quad L_{is} = L_{si} \dots (2.3.3)$$

Agar¹⁰ has discussed the requirements for the validity of Onsager's Reciprocity Relations, and Miller¹¹ has compiled a number of experimental tests of O.R.R. in various types of systems, including the non-isothermal ones.

For a simple system, describing water flow in soil under the influence of a temperature gradient, eqs. (2.3.1) reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} J_w &= L_{ww} X_w + L_{ws} X_s \\ J_s &= L_{sw} X_w + L_{ss} X_s \end{aligned} \dots (2.3.4)$$

with $L_{ws} = L_{sw}$

Here, $J_{\text{soil}}=0$ defines the reference frame, and J_w is the flux of soil-water.

Alternatively, the calorimetric heat flux J_a , may also be defined (vide. eqs. 2.2.20, 2.2.21, and 2.2.22):

$$J_w = -L_{ww} \cdot (\text{grad } \mu_w)_T - L_{wq} \cdot \frac{\text{grad } T}{T}$$

$$J_q = -L_{qw} \cdot (\text{grad } \mu_w)_T - L_{qq} \cdot \frac{\text{grad } T}{T} \dots (2.3.5)$$

(assuming the external forces F_w to be absent). This is identical with the form of phenomenological equations developed by Taylor and Cary², and has been developed here by an independent technique. For isothermal cases, $\text{grad } T=0$, and eq. (2.3.5) reduces to

$$J_w = -L_{ww} \cdot (\text{grad } \mu_w)_T$$

For one-dimensional diffusion of water,

$$(J_w)_x = -L_{ww} (d \mu_w / dx)_T \dots (2.3.6)$$

where $(J_w)_x$ is the component of J_w in x-direction. Indeed, eq. (2.3.6) expresses Darcy's law for water-flux under isothermal conditions.

Furthermore, the soil-water potential ψ_w is defined as the difference in chemical potential between the soil-water, in question, and pure free water, i.e.,

$$\psi_w = \mu_w - \mu_w^0$$

where μ_w^0 is a constant.

$$\text{Hence, } (d\mu_w / dx)_T = (d\psi_w / dx)_T$$

Therefore, it follows from eq. (2.3.6)

$$(J_w)_x = -L_{ww} (d\psi_w / dx)_T \dots (2.3.7)$$

which is yet another form of Darcy's law for water flow in unsaturated soil.

If now μ_w is assumed to be a single-valued function of water content (i.e, no hysteresis), then the gradient of μ_w in the soil system can be given by²,

$$\begin{aligned} (d\mu_w/dx)_T &= (\delta\mu_w/\delta P)_{T,\theta,n} \frac{dP}{dx} + \\ &\quad (\delta\mu_w/\delta\theta)_{T,P,n} d\theta/dx \\ &= V_w \frac{dP}{dx} + (\delta\mu_w/\delta\theta)_{T,P,n} \frac{d\theta}{dx} \quad \dots(2.3.8) \end{aligned}$$

where θ is the soil-water content on oven-dry weight basis, and V_w is the partial molal volume of water. In a saturated soil,

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\delta\mu_w/\delta\theta \right)_{T,P,n} \frac{d\theta}{dx} &= 0, \quad \text{and,} \\ (J_w)_x &= -L_{ww} V_w dP/dx \quad \dots (2.3.9) \end{aligned}$$

which is really a form of Darcy's law in saturated soils, dP/dx being the pressure-gradient.

For isothermal and isobaric conditions (unsaturated soil), one obtains from eq. (2.3.8)

$$\left(\frac{d\mu_w}{dx} \right)_T = \left(\frac{\delta\mu_w}{\delta\theta} \right)_{T,P,n} \frac{d\theta}{dx} \quad \dots (2.3.10)$$

Substitution of eq. (2.3.10) in e.q. (2.3.6) leads to

$$\begin{aligned} (J_w)_x &= -L_{ww} \left(\frac{\delta\mu_w}{\delta\theta} \right)_{T,P,n} \frac{d\theta}{dx} \\ &= -D_w \frac{d\theta}{dx} \quad \dots (2.3.11) \end{aligned}$$

where, $D_w = L_{ww} (\delta\mu_w/\delta\theta)_{T,P,n}$... (2.3.12), and is the coefficient of diffusion of water in soil.

Eq. (2.3.11) has frequently been referred to in literature as the "diffusion equation", for example, by A. A. Klute (1952), J. R. Philips (1957), W. R. Gardner and M. S. Mayhugh (1958)^{1,2}.

Turning back the attention to non-isothermal systems, it is interesting to relate the calorimetric heat flux, J_q (also called the "reduced heat" flux¹⁰), to the thermodynamic energy flux, J_u , defined by eq. (1.2.2); that is, from eq. (2.2.20).

$$\begin{aligned} J_q &= T J_s - T \sum_i J_i S_i \\ &= J_u - \sum_i \mu_i J_i - T \sum_i J_i S_i \\ &= J_u - \sum_i J_i (\mu_i + TS_i) \quad \text{(from eq. 1.2.2)} \\ &= J_u - \sum_i J_i h_i \quad \dots (2.3.13) \end{aligned}$$

where h_i is the specific enthalpy of the component "i".

Flux equations in terms of J_u and J_i may also be developed in the same way as demonstrated in sections 2.1 and 2.2. In particular, by remembering that

$$T \cdot [\text{grad} (\mu_w / T) + h_w \cdot \frac{\text{grad} T}{T}] = (\text{grad} \mu_w) T$$

and by substituting J_q in eq. (2.2.19) in terms of J_u and J_i from eq. (2.3.13), the required fluxes and forces can be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} J_u &= \text{Flux of energy,} \\ J_w &= \text{Flux of water in soil,} \\ X_w &= -T \cdot \text{grad} (\mu_w / T) \quad \dots (2.3.14) \\ X_u &= -\frac{\text{grad} T}{T} \quad \dots (2.2.15) \end{aligned}$$

At once, one may write down the linear phenomenological equations:

$$\begin{aligned} J_w &= -L_{ww} \cdot [\text{grad} (\mu_w / T)] - L_{wu} \cdot \frac{\text{grad} T}{T} \\ J_u &= -L_{uw} \cdot [\text{grad} (\mu_w / T)] - L_{uu} \cdot \frac{\text{grad} T}{T} \\ &\quad \text{with } L_{wu} = L_{uw} \quad \dots (2.3.16) \end{aligned}$$

However, it is often more convenient to work in terms of J_q rather than J_u , in dealing with heat flow problems in soil.

2.4. Heat of Transport:

Another important quantity of irreversible thermodynamics will now be introduced.

For isothermal conditions, it follows from eqs. (2.3.5)

$$\left(\frac{J_q}{J_w} \right) \text{grad} T = 0 = \frac{L_{qw}}{L_{ww}} = Q_w \quad \dots (2.4.1)$$

where Q_w is the "heat of transport (or, transfer)" of water, and is defined by eq. (2.4.1). It is, thus, seen to be the amount of heat transported by unit flux of the component, in question, under isothermal conditions. More properly, this is defined to be the amount of heat absorbed per mole of a diffusing substance from the region it leaves, and released in

Fig. 1.

the region it moves into, under isothermal conditions (and also with transport of no other component in a polycomponent system). The physical significance of this quantity can best be explained with the aid of a hypothetical experiment¹⁰.

Let a column of solution of uniform composition and temperature enclosed in a cylinder, be considered (Figure-1), and let it be divided into two halves L and R by an imaginary reference plane 00_1 . Let one mole of a particular component 'i' be now transported from L to R, across 00_1 , without affecting the temperature or pressure at any point, and also ensuring that the net amount of any other component crossing 00_1 is zero. At constant temperature and pressure the increase in entropy of R by this migration should be the partial molal entropy S_i of 'i', and the decrease in L will also be S_i . Provided the process is carried out reversibly, the net transfer of heat to the surroundings from the whole system is zero. If the process is not quasi-static, "Joule heat" from the solution has to be removed in order to keep its temperature constant, but this is quite clearly distinguished from the thermal effects which are being discussed here.

Although the net transfer of heat to the surroundings is zero, it does not follow that no heat is given out, or taken in by L and R separately, i.e., it does not necessarily follow that the transfer of one mole of 'i' will, by itself, raise the entropy of R by S_i , and cause an equal decrease in L. It is, therefore, supposed that the migration of one mole of 'i' into R increases the entropy of R by \bar{S}_i , which is then the entropy transported with one mole of 'i' under isothermal conditions. Let this be called the "transported entropy" (\bar{S}_i) of 'i'. In order that the entropy increment shall be S_i , which it must be from the definition of partial molal quantities, an amount of heat $\hat{Q}_i = T(\bar{S}_i - S_i)$ must be transferred from R to a heat reservoir, and an equal amount must be added to L in order to maintain the constancy of temperature. This amount of heat, \hat{Q}_i , is, according to the definition given above, the heat of transport of 'i'.

The entropy of transport, S_i , is then given as,

$$\hat{S}_i = \frac{\hat{Q}_i}{T} = \bar{S}_i - S_i \quad \dots (2.4.2)$$

In appendix, an extension of the above arguments, leading to a physical insight into \hat{Q}_i , to a non-isothermal system, with L and R of figure-1 maintained at different temperatures, is given.

If such transport processes were carried out in adiabatic systems, i.e., if the liquid column (figure-1) were enclosed by adiabatic walls, the temperature of one section (R) would have risen while that of

the other (L) fallen. Such setting up of temperature gradients by diffusion of matter would have been exactly the reverse situation of what is encountered in thermal diffusion. This effect, called the "Dufour effect", is observed when gases diffuse into one another isothermally; in liquids, and solids, the thermal diffusivity being much higher than the isothermal diffusion coefficients, as compared to the corresponding situation in gases, no such effect has been observed so far (although in similar condensed systems, heats of transport do make measurable contributions to Peltier heats). In soil systems also, existence of the "Dufour effect" is unlikely, and has not been reported.

It is obvious from eqs. (2.3.4) that,

$$\left(\frac{J_s}{J_w} \right) \text{grad } T = 0 = \frac{L_{bw}}{L_{ww}} = \bar{S}_w \quad (2.4.3)$$

An important point to note in this connection is that a moving component in a system (relative to a stationary background) does not necessarily carry all its partial molal entropy (S_i) with it, since some of it resides in the surrounding region, and is left behind when the particular component moves away; in other words, the entropy transported by this component, which has been termed its "transported entropy" (\bar{S}_i), is not equal to its partial molal entropy (S_i), and as a result, the entropy of transport \hat{S}_i , which is given by the difference ($\bar{S}_i - S_i$), is not zero, i.e., $\hat{Q}_i = T\hat{S}_i$ is not zero.

It is, therefore, evident that the heat of transport \hat{Q}_i is a quantity which provides a very sensitive index of interactions of various components in a mixture (not, necessarily, homogeneous).

2.5 Steady State Relations :

As briefly mentioned in section 1.2, the net flux of, say, water in soil, under a temperature gradient, vanishes at the steady state. It, therefore, follows from eq. (2.3.5) that

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d\mu_w}{d \ln T} \right)_{st} &= - \frac{L_{wq}}{L_{ww}} = - \frac{L_{qw}}{L_{ww}} \quad (\text{by O.R.R.}) \\ &= - \hat{Q}_w \quad \text{from eq. (2.4.1)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.5.1)$$

with the subscript 'st' denoting the steady state. \hat{Q}_w may thus be evaluated from a steady state experiment using eq. (2.5.1). Alternatively, \hat{Q}_w can be evaluated graphically from the slope of the plot of water potential against \log (temperature), vide. eq. (2.5.1) : this, however, holds true only over the domain of linearity between the fluxes and the forces). It is then possible to modify the flux equation, eq. (2.3.5),

incorporating \hat{Q}_w : thus,

$$\begin{aligned} (J_w)_x &= -L_{ww} \left[\left(\frac{d\mu}{dx} \right)_T - \hat{Q}_w \frac{d \ln T}{dx} \right] \\ (J_q)_x &= -L_{ww} \hat{Q}_w \left(\frac{d\mu_w}{dx} \right)_T - L_{qq} \frac{d \ln T}{dx} \end{aligned} \quad (2.5.2)$$

These equations are again identical with those derived by Taylor and Cary². Thus, the diagonal coefficients, L_{ww} and L_{qq} , in eqs. (2.5.2), can be determined from the simultaneous measurements of the gradients of chemical potential of water, and the temperature, along with the fluxes of water and heat. Once L_{ww} and L_{qq} have been determined, the coupling coefficient L_{wq} (or, L_{qw}) can be calculated from eq. (2.4.1). Eqs. (2.5.2) may then be used,

with knowledge of L_{ww} , L_{qq} , and \hat{Q}_w , to predict the water and heat fluxes in soil. In order to use the "diffusion equations" to predict these fluxes with the aid of knowledge of D_w , let us consider eqs. (2.3.5) in terms of the diffusion coefficient (D_w) of water,

$$(J_w)_x = -D_w \frac{d\theta}{dx} - L_{wq} \frac{d \ln T}{dx} \quad \dots (2.5.3)$$

where D_w is given by eq. (2.3.12). At the steady state, $(J_w)_x = 0$; hence from eq. (2.5.3),

$$\left(\frac{d\theta}{d \ln T} \right)_{st} = -L_{wq}/D_w = -\beta \text{ (say)} \quad (2.5.4)$$

Combining eqs. (2.5.3) and (2.5.4),

$$(J_w)_x = -D_w \left[\frac{d\theta}{dx} + \beta \frac{d \ln T}{dx} \right] \quad \dots (2.5.5)$$

and, similarly, by using O.R.R. ($L_{wq} = L_{qw}$),

$$(J_q)_x = -D_w \beta \frac{d\theta}{dx} - L_{qq} \frac{d \ln T}{dx} \quad \dots (2.5.6)$$

Eqs. (2.5.5) and (2.5.6) are of the same form as those derived by Philip and de Vries (1957)^{1,2} who developed their equations through a detailed analysis rather than a special case of a more general treatment as has been done in this article. Cassel *et al.*³ have also used these "diffusion equations" to determine J_w through Columbia fine sandy loam.

3.1. Thermal Diffusion of Water Vapour :

Cary and Taylor¹ developed phenomenological equations for fluxes of heat and water vapour in unsaturated soils, using the form of dissipation function in terms of J_u and J_w (vide. eqs. 2.3.16). By considering a series of substitutions and approximations, and by assuming a constant value of 75.3 J. Mol⁻¹. K⁻¹, for C_p of moist soil (in the tempera-

ture range of 0°C to 45°C), they arrived at the following equations for $(J_w)_x$ and $(J_u)_x$:

$$\begin{aligned} (J_w)_x &= A_w \log T + B_w (1/T) \\ (J_u)_x &= D_u \log T + D_u (1/T) \end{aligned} \quad \dots (3.1.1)$$

where the various coefficients are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} A_w &= 0.82 \times 10^{10} L_{ww} \\ B_w &= 5.68 \times 10^8 (L_{wu} - 2.23 \times 10^4 L_{ww}) \\ C_u &= L_{uu} - 2.23 \times 10^4 L_{uw} \\ D_u &= 173 L_{uw} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (3.1.2)$$

The simultaneous heat water (vapour) fluxes at the steady state were measured with two different thermal gradients, and these, on substitution in eqs. (3.1.1), yielded the values of A_w , B_w , C_u and D_u , whence the L-coefficients were calculated, using eqs. (3.1.2). The ratio L_{wu}/L_{uw} was found to vary from 0.89 to 1.01 for various soils, illustrating thereby the validity of O.R.R. in such coupled transport processes in soil.

The same authors¹ were also able to separate the vapour and liquid-phase components of water flux in Millville loam soil, and demonstrate the validity of O.R.R. for these different types of water flows. It is interesting to note from this latter piece of work that the coupling coefficients, L_{wu} and L_{uw} , are numerically much higher for the liquid-phase transfer of soil-water.

Cary^{1,3} has also developed more rigorous relations for the heat and mass transfer through air, using an experimental set-up similar to one used by Taylor and Cary¹ to study thermal diffusion in soil. However, these relations are not of direct relevance to the present topic, and are not discussed here. A detailed review of various aspects of relevant thermal diffusion experiments by different workers has already appeared^{1,4} and may be referred to for further details.

3.2. Non-linear Flux Equations :

The relationships so far developed assume a linearity between various fluxes and forces (as discussed in section 1.2). However, such linear relations are, in fact, limiting cases, valid only for small departures from equilibrium, of more general non-linear phenomenological relations between J 's, and X 's. Such relations depend, for their applications in practical systems, on the symmetry of the matrix of higher-order phenomenological coefficients, in addition to Onsager's relations. In particular, for transport studies in soil, the various anomalous departures from Darcy's law may conveniently be discussed in terms of these higher-order phenomono-

logical coefficients. An exhaustive review^{1,2} has appeared on this particular aspect which will be skipped off here for the sake of brevity. It may, however, be mentioned that the reported work, for example, by Hadas and Taylor (1968), has failed to show the validity of second-order symmetry relations, although O.R.R. has been found to hold good, in these more general experiments, with reasonable accuracy^{1,2}.

4.1. Design of Experiments :

Experimental investigations may be carried out to study thermal diffusion of water through clays in sodium and hydrogen form with temperature gradients kept as small as possible in order to avoid the nonlinearity in flux equations. In addition to testing the validity of Onsager's Reciprocity Relations in such transport processes, special emphasis is to be laid on the evaluation of the heat of transport of water, \hat{Q}_w , in order to utilise such values of \hat{Q}_w to predict the nature of interaction between clays and water (vide. section 2.4). It should be possible to draw correlation between \hat{Q}_w , determined in this manner, and the p^F -clay-content relations which have already been investigated by various workers, using different techniques. Furthermore, the bonding (nature and strength) of water to clay surfaces may be inferred from such studies, which may possibly throw additional light on the availability of the so-called "hygroscopic water" to plants under conditions of moisture stress.

Such experiments can be extended to cover transport of water under a temperature gradient across oil humus fractions, and soils with different contents of humus. In case of extreme success of such studies, one might even hope to add these \hat{Q}_w values to the various characteristics of soil, such as, water-holding capacity, field-capacity, wilting point, etc., which are taken to indicate the retention of soilwater at different degrees of saturation. However, \hat{Q}_w may be expected to be a better guide (or, atleast, a supplementary guide) in this context in that it offers an understanding of the mechanism of retention (i.e., through "making" or "breaking" of 'local' water-structure in the vicinity of soil particles), in addition to being a quantitative index of water-retention.

As a supporting study, the viscosity-B-coefficient of Jones-Dole's equation^{1,6}, viz. eq. (4.1.1)

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + B C + \dots \quad (4.1.1)$$

where η and η_0 and the viscosity coefficients of the suspension (of concentration C) and pure water, respectively, at the same temperature, and A , B are empirical constants, may be determined in the

aqueous suspension of humic acids and soil with various humus-contents. As is well known, A in eq. (4.1.1) gives a measure of "solute-solute" interactions (can be neglected for dilute suspensions), and B measures the "solute-solvent" interactions, i. e. B is related to the modification of "micro-viscosity" of water in the neighbourhood of the disperse phase particles, as compared to bulk-viscosity, and thus is analogous to the heat of transport, \hat{Q}_w . However, a polyphase nature of humic acid suspension should be given due consideration in such evaluations, and the resulting A and B coefficients of eq. (4.1.1) may well, in that case, be composite quantities. A less complicated situation in this respect is expected for the earlier fractions in humic acid condensation process, e.g., fulvic acid, which are known to exist predominantly in single phase in aqueous suspensions.

In view of the consideration that the thermal mobility of water molecules increases with rise in temperature, both the structure-promoting influence (with a positive contribution to \hat{Q}_w) and the structure-disruptive influence (with a negative contribution to \hat{Q}_w) of solute particles are likely to diminish at enhanced temperatures, and as a result, the sign and magnitude of the temperature coefficient, ($d\hat{Q}_w/dT$), may provide yet another index (in addition to \hat{Q}_w itself) of solute-solvent interactions. In this approach, it will also be interesting to seek correlation between ($d\hat{Q}_w/dT$) and the temperature coefficient of the viscosity B-coefficient, (dB/dT).

Appendix :

Let the liquid column of figure-1 be considered once more, and let the regions L and R be maintained at different temperatures, say at T_1 and T_2 , respectively. In order that the arguments given in section 2.4 can be extended to such a non-isothermal system, separate heats (and, entropies) of transport, \hat{Q}_1 and \hat{Q}_2 (and, \hat{S}_1 and \hat{S}_2), corresponding to the temperatures T_1 and T_2 , must be assigned, and then it is required to show that the mean of \hat{Q}_1 and \hat{Q}_2 (say, \hat{Q}_M) satisfies the relation, $\hat{Q}_M = T_M \hat{S}_M$, where T_M and \hat{S}_M are the mean values of these quantities for the sections L and R, separately.

In other words, it is required to show,

$$\hat{Q}_M = \frac{1}{2} (T_1 + T_2) \frac{1}{2} (\hat{S}_1 + \hat{S}_2)$$

$$i.e., \frac{1}{2} (\hat{Q}_1 + \hat{Q}_2) = \frac{1}{2} (T_1 + T_2) (\hat{S}_1 + \hat{S}_2)$$

$$i.e., T_1 \hat{S}_1 + T_2 \hat{S}_2 = \frac{1}{2} (T_1 \hat{S}_1 + T_2 \hat{S}_1 + T_1 \hat{S}_2 + T_2 \hat{S}_2)$$

$$i.e., T_1 \hat{S}_1 + T_2 \hat{S}_1 = T_2 \hat{S}_1 + T_1 \hat{S}_2 \quad (i)$$

Putting, $\hat{S}_2 = \hat{S}_1 + d\hat{S}$, or, $d\hat{S} = \hat{S}_2 - \hat{S}_1$ (ii),

and, $T_2 = T_1 + dT$, or, $dT = T_2 - T_1$ (iii),

the left-hand side of eq. (i) becomes,

$$\begin{aligned} & T_1 \hat{S}_1 + (T_1 + dT) (\hat{S}_1 + d\hat{S}) \\ &= T_1 \hat{S}_1 + T_1 \hat{S}_1 + \hat{S}_1 dT + T_1 d\hat{S} + d\hat{S} dT \\ &\simeq 2T_1 \hat{S}_1 + \hat{S}_1 (T_2 - T_1) + T_1 (\hat{S}_2 - \hat{S}_1) \\ &\quad \text{using eqs. (ii) and (iii)} \end{aligned}$$

(neglecting the term $d\hat{S}dT$, which is small as compared to other terms)

$$\begin{aligned} &= 2T_1 \hat{S}_1 + T_2 \hat{S}_1 - T_1 \hat{S}_1 + T_1 \hat{S}_2 - T_1 \hat{S}_1 \\ &= T_2 \hat{S}_1 + T_1 \hat{S}_2 \\ &= \text{Right-hand side of eq. (i).} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the required result.

Indeed, in this case, heat will be transferred across 00_1 (fig.1) from a heat reservoir at T_1 to another at a different temperature T_2 , and this is thermodynamically significant.

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Roman capital letters in italics denote vectors